

ANALYSIS OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES IN JSC "KHOVRENKO" OF SAMARKAND REGION

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Abstract. In this article, the analysis of economic and financial indicators of the company's products, the products, and the fact that they are intended for a wide range of the population, are considered.

Keywords: enterprise, wine products, market, economic, financial, trade, warehouse, commodity, district.

АНАЛИЗ МАРКЕТИНГОВОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В АО «ХОВРЕНКО» САМАРКАНДСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассмотрен анализ экономических и финансовых показателей продукции компании, продукции, а также того, что она предназначена для широкого круга населения.

Ключевые слова: предприятие, винодельческая продукция, рынок, хозяйственный, финансовый, торговый, складской, товарный, район.

INTRODUCTION

Samarkand region is engaged in the cultivation of grape wines and the production of alcoholic beverages from them. Since the climate and natural conditions of the region are very gray, there are several wine production enterprises in Samarkand city and region. One of them is the wine production enterprise called Khovrenko OJSC.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Today, JSC "Khovrenko" occupies a special place in the region in terms of its composition and manufactured products. The enterprise has a wine materials shop, a cognac shop, a souvenir shop, a distillery shop, transport and construction - repair shops, three finished product warehouses, two mechanical workshops, two base and tara (container) shops.

The first processing department of the enterprise carries out the activities of receiving and processing grapes, producing wine materials, storing and keeping them, and sending semi-finished wine materials to the combine that require technological processing of wine materials.

The wine materials workshop, the first processing department of the enterprise and the wine points brings the wine materials to a ready state, if necessary, puts the finished wine materials into storage.

The Samarkand wine production enterprise named "Khovrenko" is a legal entity according to the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan. He has assets accounted for in his independent balance sheet, has property and personal immovable rights on his own behalf, and can assume obligations, be a plaintiff and be liable in court.

"Khovrenko" OJSC production enterprise is one of the most prestigious wine production enterprises of our Republic and Asia. The enterprise mainly specializes in the production of wine, cognac, alcohol products, and is currently one of the companies operating at full capacity. In the conditions of the market economy, there are few enterprises that can withstand

competition. Market laws try to force not only manufacturing enterprises, but also trade and service enterprises from the market, because market laws have an objective nature, and regardless of whether it is a legal entity or an individual, it is necessary to settle with the market. Because this is a mandatory condition. It is guaranteed that every manufacturing enterprise will win in the competition if it properly studies the market laws and adjusts its business accordingly. Personnel employees of the "Khovrenko" production enterprise thoroughly study the market rules, determine whether there is a demand for their goods, and then start production. In this way, they prevent the shortage of goods. Currently, the "Khovrenko" enterprise produces 5 different assortments of cognac products, 6-8 different assortments of wine products, 15-18 types of liquor-vodka products.

The products produced by the enterprise fully meet the requirements of the State standard. Currently, it is very important, because the struggle for quality is the demand of the times.

JSC "Khovrenko" production enterprise has its customers not only in the domestic market, but also in the foreign market. These include: Kazakhstan, Russia, Belarus. The fact that the enterprise is engaged in export and import indicates that it produces quality products.

In addition, there are nine wine pre-processing points and factories at the Khovrenko OJSC production enterprise.

- Khaidarov point in Samarkand district - 2.21 ha
- Muminabad point in Urgut district - 1.4 ha.
- Point in Urgut - 0.98 to.
- Point "Friday market" in Tailoq district - 1.5 ha
- "Soj" plant in Tailoq district - 2.7 ha
- "Shirin" factory in Pastdargom district - 1.75 ha
- "Gulya Kandoz" factory in Pastdargom district - 1.7ha
- "Aq-tepa" point in Koshrabot district - 3.0 ha.
- "Koradaryo" point in Kattakorgan district - 0.75 ha

Primary wine processing points and factories mainly receive grapes, process them, prepare wine products, send wine to warehouses for storage, timely delivery and aging.

Currently, three groups of grape juices are produced in the juice production cooperative society: "stolovaya", "krepkoe" and "desertnoe".

Each group of juices, in turn, is divided into branded (expiration not less than two years) and ordinary or ordinary juices. Types of "Stolovoe" juices;

a) Stolovaya ordinary juices "BayanShirey", "Bogi Maidan", "Saperavi", "Rkatsiteli" - with a strength of 9-12°.

b) Branded table - «Cabernet juice 9-12°.

Types of "Krepkoe" juices.

a) Ordinary juices "Port-53", "Uzbekistan", 18-19° strength and 8-9% sugar content.

Types of dessert juices:

a) Dessert simple juices "Muskat", "Uzbekistan", "Gulnora", "Tokay", "Kagor" 14-16° strength with 18-20% sugar.

b) Dessert brand juices "Shirin", "Aleatiko", "Uzbekistan", "Gulya-Kandoz" with 16% strength and 22-25% sugar content.

In addition to juices, cognac and liqueur - alcoholic products are also produced in Khaysdarsk society:

a. Cognacs - "Korona Imperii", "Samarkand", "Sherdor", "Tilla Kori", Filatov with a strength of 40-42°, a sugar content of 1.2-1.5% and a shelf life of 4-12 years.

b. Alcoholic liquor products - vodkas such as Samarkand, Russkiy yuvelir, Zolotaya snopa, Russkaya, Pshenichnaya, Chistoe zoloto, Chistoe srebro, Bratya, Russkiy stil, Zarafshon, Tron, Marokand, Grad, Shik, Blesk, Ermitage with a strength of more than 40°, "Samarkand balm".

RESULTS

It can be seen that by the present time, JSC Khovrenko juice production enterprise is making great efforts to increase the volume and range of products.

When analyzing the activities of OJSC, we first considered the production activities. In 2019-2021, the company produced wine, alcohol, cognac and liqueur - alcoholic beverages in the following quantities.

Table 1

The amount of product production at the production enterprise "Khovrenko" OJSC thousand DAL

t/r	Product name	Production, by years			in 2021 compared to 2019, %
		2019	2020	2021	
1	Grape juice	71	100	101	142.2
2	Cognac	6	9	10.3	172.0
3	Liquor-vodka products	404	419	442	109.4
4	Cognac alcohol	9.8	21.6	16.8	171.4
5	Development of wine raw materials	208.7	139.6	146.3	70.1

As can be seen from this table, the production volume was increased in 2019-2021. The production of grape juice increased by 142.2%, and the production of brandy increased by 172%. At the same time, the production of wine raw materials has decreased significantly. The reason for this is that competitors have launched the production of this product. Buying alcohol from abroad requires a lot of money and cannot be done by the company.

The total volume of product production is shown in Table 2.

Table 2

The general indicator of the production enterprise "Khovrenko" OJSC, mln. amount

t/r	Indicators	Amount by years			in 2021 compared to 2019, %
		2019	2020	2021	
1	Merchandise at current prices	7763.6	9131.7	9823.3	126.5
2	Commodity products at comparable prices	5906.4	9035.0	9823.3	166.3
3	The finished product is sold at prices	13408.1	19280.5	20643, 1	153.9

It can be seen that the general indicators increased by 126.5% compared to 2019, while the sale of finished products increased by 153.9%. The main factors of this are the increase in prices and the implementation of the export plan.

An important part of the economic analysis is related to the analysis of the efficiency of human resources. Analyzing labor performance requires looking at the number of employees, labor productivity, and average monthly wages.

Table 3

Dynamics of labor indicators at the production enterprise "Khovrenko" OJSC.

t/r	Indicators	Unit of measure	Amount by years			in 2021 compared to 2019, %
			2019	2020	2021	
1	The average number of employees on the list	person	220	236	235	106.8
2	Labor productivity	million soums	36.3	40.6	41.8	115.1
3	Labor fund	million soums	539.3	662.4	791.0	146.7
4	Average monthly salary	thousand soums	244.2	244.9	280.5	114.9

As can be seen from the table, the number of employees decreased compared to the plan in the last year, which led to a relative increase in cocktail productivity. At the same time, labor productivity increased by only 15.1% in three years, which is a very low indicator in current conditions. The average monthly salary is also not guaranteed to grow sufficiently.

DISCUSSION

In the analysis of financial indicators, we considered the state of the company's balance sheet. It is known that the assets and liabilities of the 2021 balance sheet are 1,756,047 thousand soums, which is an increase of 291 thousand soums compared to the beginning of the year. This was mainly achieved by increasing current assets by 289,900 soums. In particular, stocks of goods and materials were increased by 113,000 soums, production reserves by 80,000 soums, unfinished production by 174,900 soums. Finished product balances decreased by 141.9 thousand soums, and receivables increased by 178.4 thousand soums.

The profit from the sale is 858.9 thousand soums, where the excise tax is 313 million soums, and the VAT is 143 million soums. Net profit is 402.2 million. formed 165.2 million soums, which is 165.2 million more than last year's figure. a lot of sums.

Last season's expenses were 96.4 mln. 54.6 million soums compared to last year. a lot of soums, this is mainly 61.7 mln. soums were in exchange for "Other operating expenses".

85.6% of the product export plan set by the company "Ozmevasabzavotuzumsanoatholding" was fulfilled. In particular, instead of the specified 125,000 US dollars, products were exported in the amount of 107,000 US dollars. The change compared to 2020 was 19.3%.

The non-fulfillment of the product export plan is explained by the insufficient availability of cognac alcohol and Sukhoi wine materials, which are in high demand in the foreign market.

The products produced by JSC "Khovrenko" are intended for a wide range of people, and their income level is also taken into account. The enterprise is distinguished by the high level of taste of its products and also has 36 different types of medals.

In addition, branded dessert wine "Gulya Kandoz" won an international certificate at the world exhibition held in the USA.

CONCLUSIONS

In order to improve the activity of the production enterprise named "Khovrenko", it is recommended to pay attention to the following areas:

- purchase of agricultural products from legal entities and individuals by money transfer or cash payment, to store, process and sell them for profit;
- receiving and selling any goods not prohibited by the laws of the republic from legal entities and individuals in the territory of the republic by exchanging them for other goods, processing agricultural products for winemaking;
- expansion of marketing activities, especially the correct use of marketing principles when selling to foreign countries.

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